

New Covenant Church Nigeria

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Pentecostal, Language, Atlantic-Congo, Indo-European, Volta-Congo, Classical Indo-European, Benue-Congo, Germanic, Defoid, Northwest Germanic, Yoruboid, West Germanic, Edekiri, North Sea Germanic, Ede, Anglo-Frisian, Eastern Ede, Anglic, Southeastern Ede, Later Anglic, Nuclear Yoruba, Middle-Modern English, Lucumi-Yoruba, Macro-English, Yoruba, English, New Religiosity, Christian

This poll is about a religious organisation called, the New Covenant Church that began in Nigeria in October 1985. The first worship meeting of the religious organisation held at the Women Training Centre, Samonda, Ibadan in Nigeria. Rev Paul Jinadu is the founder of the religious body. The New Covenant Church has at least 500 branches across the globe which includes countries in Africa, Europe, America, Asia and the Middle East. The United Kingdom branch began in 1986 at the Elephant and Castle, London. Nigeria has the highest concentration of the church branches because it has over four hundred of those branches. The Apex leaders, Rev & Mrs. Paul Jinadu are assisted by an Associate General Overseer, Rev Emmanuel O. Ajao. The two Deputy Overseers are Rev Obafemi Omisade (overseeing Europe and North America) and Rev Olufemi Oyelade (overseeing Africa and other parts of the world). The group aims to make disciples of Jesus Christ from all nations on earth. The mission of the organisation is to build city churches around the world that will be at least 1% of the local population which will enable the church to influence their community positively. Furthermore, they hope to lead all group members to maturity in Christ and foster meaningful fellowship among group members. They believe in one church, one foundation and biblical pattern. This group has the following ministry group: Liberty international, Covenant Women International, Children/Teenage Ministry and Youth Ministry. The New Covenant Church work towards growing a church branch to become a conference (self-financing, self-governing and self-propagating) that begins to pioneer other satellites churches far or near and there are 14 of such conferences in Nigeria. The National Administrative Office of the group is opposite Customs Quarters, Ijokodo, Ibadan, Nigeria. Available in print for the religious group are discipleship materials that include, 7 Reasons why every Christian should speak in tongues, Believers Bible Class, Freedom from Bondage and New life in Christ. Available finance and official materials include, NCC Manual for Accounting and The Constitution.

Date Range: 1985 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria, Oyo state, Ogun State, Ekiti State, Osun state, Osun State, Lagos, Ondo state, Oyo state, Kwara state

This map includes the approximate regions of Southwest/Western Nigeria and is comprised of the following states: Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, Ekiti, and Benin states. The additional inclusion of the West Central region state of Kwara is to the north of these states.

Entry Perspective

✓ Orthodoxy

Sources

Academic (peer-reviewed) sources related to the subject matter:

ID:

Attach PDFs if available in digital format.

11403

– Source 1:: About Us - New Covenant Church Nigeria - newcovenantchurchnigeria.org

– Source 2:: Rev Dr Paul Jinadu - General Overseer - www.nccdouglasville.org

– Source 3:: Our History - New Covenant Church, Winnipeg. nccwinnipeg.org

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Media and third sector sources related to the subject matter:

ID: 11404

Attach PDFs if available in digital format.

– Source 1:: <https://newcovenantchurchnigeria.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/pastor-kate-jinadu.jpeg>

– Source 2:: <https://nccwinnipeg.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/d7a5ac9e-26e1-47be-918a-67a8852eef9b.jpg>

– Source 3:: <https://nccwinnipeg.org/blog/>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

List the top three most important religious texts for this religious movement

ID: 11405

Attach PDFs if available in digital format.

– Source 1:: The Holy Bible

– Source 2:: The Constitution of the Registered Trustees of New Covenant Church - <https://newcovenantchurchnigeria.org/resources/>

– Source 3:: The Blue Book 4th Edition January 2018 - <https://newcovenantchurchnigeria.org/resources/>

– Other:: New Life in Christ - <https://newcovenantchurchnigeria.org/resources/>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

List the locations of any key archives relating to this movement

ID:

11406

– List locations: Headquarters Address: NCC Campground, Opposite Customs Quarters, Ijokodo, Ibadan.

Notes: The national headquarters of the New Covenant Church Nigeria is located at the NCC Campground, opposite Customs Quarters, Ijokodo-Apete Road, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The national administrative office is situated in the same area, with a P.M.B 5450, Dugbe, Ibadan.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

General Variables

Date Range

On what basis was the date range selected?

ID: 9727

– Founding period

Notes: The date range is between 1985 to 2026 because the New Covenant Church Nigeria started in October 1985. The religious body's growth expanded across the globe and has continued till date.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Religious Tradition

Is this entry focused on a transnational religious movement?

ID: 9728

Transnational - addressing an audience that transcends nation state identity or a particular ethnic/regional diasporic population

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church is presently reported to have over 500 branches of the Church in Africa, Europe, America, Middle East and Asia.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is this entry focused on a global religious movement?

ID: 9729

Global - addressing a particular ethnic or national diasporic identity that is dispersed globally

– Yes

Notes: Although at least 400 of the over 500 branches of the Church is located Nigeria, the remaining over 100 branches are spread across Africa, Europe, America, Middle East and Asia.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is this entry focused on a specific national context of the religious movement? ID: 9730

— Yes

Notes: The entry focuses majorly on the New Covenant Church as a religious organisation in the context of Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Regardless of scholarly classification, does the religious movement understand itself as part of a larger religious tradition? ID: 9731

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9732

— Christian

Notes: The New Covenant Church group understand itself as belonging to the larger christian religious tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the religious movement a member of any overarching religious organisation or tradition? ID: 9733

— Yes Comment: The New Covenant Church belongs to a broader Christian movement connected to the Pentecostal/Charismatic Movement. They also belong to the Evangelical Christian tradition.

Notes: the Pentecostal/Charismatic Movement emphasises spiritual gifts and personal relationship with God. They Evangelical Christian tradition focuses on spreading the gospel message and holding onto the biblical authority for faith and practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement engage in interfaith work? ID: 9734

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Select all that apply

ID: 9735

– Interfaith humanitarian projects

– Religious reconciliation initiatives

Notes: The Liberty International which is a ministry arm of the New Covenant Church channels global aid and organizes programmes providing free medical care and clean water, promotes agricultural and business empowerment across religious lines. The International President of Liberty International is Rev.(Mrs) Kate Jinadu.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

State and Society

Is there violent conflict (within the geographical area under consideration)?

ID: 9737

– Yes

Notes: The Nigerian state where the New Covenant Church group is domiciled does experience continuous attacks from bandits, armed herdsmen and terrorists who on the basis of their extreme religious ideology kill, kidnap or maim innocent residence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the country have an official state religion or religions?

ID:
9738

– No

Notes: The country is a secular state. Nigeria has no official or state religion

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is the religious movement's legal system the same as the country's legal system?

ID:
9742

– Yes

Notes: The religious group operate within the country's legal provisions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the country have a secular government?

ID: 9743

A secular government maintains institutional separation between religion and state affairs.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement maintain a separate legal system that operates alongside national law and addresses civil matters? ID: 9744

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church is guided by her own constitution, policies and practices. They however do not disregard the national legal system as far as it does not conflict with their religious faith.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is the religious movement formally recognised by the state ?

ID: 9745

This could be positive or negative recognition

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the religious movement an officially registered religion? ID: 9746

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church is registered with the Corporate Affairs Commission in Nigeria as a religious organisation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the religious movement a charity/non-profit? ID: 9747

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church religious group operate as a non-profit organisation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the religious movement a company? ID: 9748

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the religious movement considered a political religious movement? ID: 9749

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the religious movement considered a terrorist or proscribed organisation? ID: 9750

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the religious movement considered any other type of organisation? ID: 9751

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have official political support? ID: 9752

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have social recognition as a 'religion' among the general population in this country? ID: 9754

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have close affiliation with a political party?

ID: 9755

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement actively discourage members from political participation ?

ID: 9757

Political participation includes voting, running for office, holding office and forms of political activism.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage its members to serve in the military?

ID:

– 0 Unclear views, neutral

9762

Notes: The group is neutral about members joining the military or not.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement broadly support nativism ?

ID:

Nativism is a political ideology that favors the interests of native-born or established inhabitants over immigrants. In some cases, it entails the belief that immigrants are not legitimate members of the state.

9763

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement teach that the national government should become more aligned with the religious movement's beliefs and practices?

ID: 9765

– Yes

Notes: The religious group do proselyte and teach that the national government should become more aligned with their religious belief and practices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is direct political engagement perceived to bring closer alignment?

ID:

– Yes 9766

Notes: The group advocate more opportunities for members to be involve in direct political engagement.

↳ Is peaceful protest perceived to bring closer alignment? ID: 9767

– Yes

Notes: The group does not forbid members engaging in peaceful protest.

↳ Are rituals or magic used by the religious movement to encourage closer alignment? ID: 9768

– No

↳ Is direct action encouraged to bring about closer alignment? ID: 9769

Direct action includes property destruction and sabotage, forms of civil disobedience and non-cooperation, and symbolic acts such as hunger strikes, self-immolation and burning military draft cards.

– Yes

Notes: Group members are encouraged to engage in direct actions such as voting at elections and attending public hearings.

↳ Is violent direct action ever encouraged to bring about closer alignment? ID: 9770

– No

Notes: The group does not encourage any form of violence to bring about closer alignment.

Does the religious movement teach that the current national government should be replaced? ID: 9771

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement describe itself as being persecuted or facing discrimination ? ID: 9773

If answering for a particular national context, consider that context only. If answer for a globalised context, answer in the global context.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the religious movement claimed to have experienced restrictions on group assembly? ID: 9774

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church face existential threat from non state actors like Boko Haram extremists groups and ISWAP groups.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the religious movement claimed to have experienced restrictions on registering marriages? ID: 9775

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the religious movement claimed to have experienced restrictions on membership? ID: 9776

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the religious movement claimed to have experienced direct discrimination of its members? ID: 9777

Direct discrimination includes employment, housing, education, government services, healthcare and finances.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the religious movement claimed to have experienced indirect discrimination of its members? ID: 9778

Indirect discrimination includes stereotyping, regulations on the education of minors, professional networking barriers, micro-aggressions, digital discrimination, and restricted work and social

opportunities due to mandatory religious practices and holy days.

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the religious movement claimed to have experienced sensational media coverage? ID: 9779

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the religious movement claimed to have experienced other types of restrictions? ID: 9780

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria claim to have experienced restriction on proselyting people of the Islamic faith.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Has the religious movement experienced state-sanctioned violence? ID: 9781

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is the religious movement viewed as having committed normative or legal violations? ID: 9783

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Has the religious movement experienced state-sanctioned interventions? ID: 9785

– Yes

Notes: The state uses lawful authority and resources to protect the New Covenant Church, her members and her property the same way it does for any citizen or institution.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members generally feel safe publicly identifying with the religious movement? ID: 9786

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a derogatory term that people commonly use to describe the religious movement? ID: 9787

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a term that the movement uses for its members? ID: 9789

– Yes [specify]: Brother/Sister in Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a term that the movement uses for non-members? ID: 9790

– Yes [specify]: UnBelievers

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about the relationship between the state and the religious movement that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9791

– Specify: There is nothing important about the relationship between the state and the religious movement that has not been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Origins/Founder

When was the religious movement founded? ID: 9792

– Write date or date range: The New Covenant Church religious group was founded in 1985.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Primary language of the religious movement:

ID:

Note to DRH team - Can this be less confusing to find the main linguistic groups in the world today than it was when Ted and I looked at it in April?

9793

– Primary language: English language is commonly used and any language that fits the context of a particular branch of the New Covenant Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

In which contemporary country was the religious movement founded?

ID:

– Specify: The New Covenant Church was founded in Nigeria.

9794

Notes: The New Covenant Church was founded in Ibadan, Nigeria. The first worship held at the venue of the Women Training Centre, Samonda.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Write any historical or alternative names for the country:

ID: 9795

– Specify: There is no specific alternative name for the country.

Notes: Since the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern protectorate in 1914, the country has been known as Nigeria - no alternative name.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are specific places important to the founding story of this religious movement?

ID:

– Yes

9796

Notes: The Women Training Centre, Samonda where the first worship service held is of great importance to the founding story of this religious group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there an identifiable founder of the religious movement? (Answer more than once if ID: 9797

multiple founders)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ **Name:** ID: 9798
– Write name: Rev Dr Paul Jinadu is the founder of the Covenant Church religious movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ **Birth Date:** ID: 9799
– Write birth date:: Rev Dr Paul Jinadu was born in 1942

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ **Sex:** ID: 9800
– Male

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ **Primary language of founder:** ID: 9801
– Write primary language:: Yoruba language is the primary language of Paul Jinadu the Founder of New Covenant Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ **Ethnicity** ID: 9802
– Write ethnicity:: Paul Jinadu is of the Yoruba Ethnic Group.

Notes: The Yoruba ethnic group are predominant in the South-western part of Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a symbolic or visual representation of the founder or founders? ID: 9803
— Yes

Notes: The pictures of the founder and his wife is commonly displayed in offices and branches of the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Were the founder or founders part of an existing religious tradition? ID: 9804
— Yes

Notes: The Founding couple (Paul and Kate Jinadu) worked with the Apostolic Church and Foursquare Gospel Church (which are both of the Christian tradition) as preachers and church planters before moving out to begin the New Covenant Church Movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Did the founder or founders claim direct communication with supernatural powers as a source of guidance for starting the religious movement? ID: 9805
— Yes

Notes: Paul Jinadu lay claim to supernatural encounter with Jesus Christ that led to his conversion from Islam and later led to the starting of the New Covenant Church planting.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are the founder or founders considered to be human? ID: 9806
— Yes

Notes: Paul Jinadu and Kate Jinadu are considered to be humans who have relationship with a divinity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are the founder or founders considered to be other or 'more' than human? ID: 9807
— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is the founder considered a prophet or divine intermediary?

ID:
9809

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Were the founder or founders believed to have spiritual or supernatural abilities?

ID: 9810

– Yes

Notes: The founders are believed to be divinely empowered to lead and perform other fatherly roles.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Did the founder or founders prophesise about the future?

ID: 9811

– No

Notes: The founder is mainly committed to preaching the content of the Holy Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are the founder or founders considered infallible?

ID:
9812

– No

Notes: The founders are not considered to be infallible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are the founder or founders still alive?

ID:
9813

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the founder or founders live in exile from their country of origin?

ID: 9814

– No

Notes: Though born in Nigeria, they later moved to the UK and continue to coordinate their movement from there.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Has the founder or founders appointed successors? ID: 9815

– No

Notes: There is no known appointed successor by the founder..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are the founder or founders deceased? ID: 9817

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members value the founder's biography as sacred or as a source of religious knowledge? ID: 9824

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Sources of Authority and Texts

List the top three most important religious texts. ID: 9825

Texts may or may not be written- they could be man-made objects, oral traditions or natural features - but are considered to be central to the recording and remembering of the religious movement's belief and/or practices.

– Source 1:: The Holy Bible

– Source 2:: The Constitution of the Registered Trustees of the New Covenant Church.

– Source 3:: The Blue Book 4th Edition January 2018.

– Other:: New Life in Christ

Notes: The Holy Bible remains the sole source of authority for faith and practice in the New Covenant Church, everything else draws inspiration from it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have there been revisions to key religious texts?

ID: 9826

– No

Notes: The main religious text which is the Holy Bible they believe should not be subject to revision.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are religious texts considered ancient by the religious movement (even if assessed differently by experts)? ID: 9828

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Bible which is over 2000 years old is considered an ancient and yet relevant religious texts for all the movement's activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a believed origin of religious texts?

ID: 9829

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply

ID:
9830

- Canonised
- Collective revelations
- Divine revelations
- Prophetic visions
- Spirit mediumship

Notes: They believe the Holy Bible is written by people who were inspired by the Spirit of God, a divine revelation given to various writers over centuries and was later canonized.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a hierarchy of knowledge whereby deeper teachings are accessible only as members advance? ID: 9831

– Yes

Notes: Members are expected to grow from one level of knowledge to another as they remain in the

group. The discipleship programme is designed to teach different level of knowledge base on the spiritual level of each member.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are authoritative religious texts still being created?

ID: 9832

– No

Notes: The Bible is the final revelation and authoritative text the group rely on. Any other text used by the group is drawn from the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are some religious texts considered free from error (infallible and inerrant)?

ID: 9834

– Yes

Notes: The Bible which the main religious text of the group is considered infallible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a formal process or institution for interpreting religious texts?

ID:

– Yes

9835

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members highly value the interpretation of religious texts by religious authorities?

ID: 9836

– Yes

Notes: Although all members have the freedom to read and interpret the Bible, however, leaders who have vast training in that regard are highly valued.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are individuals encouraged to interpret religious texts for themselves?

ID:

– Yes

9837

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members encouraged to study texts or materials beyond those created by the religious movement? ID: 9838

– Yes

Notes: The group texts beyond that of the religious movement that members would read should not contradict the teachings and believe of the New Covenant Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is direct personal experience valued as a source of religious knowledge? ID: 9839

– Yes

Notes: The group believe that God can speak and inspire individuals including their leaders through revelations and visions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is channelled authority valued as a source of religious knowledge? ID: 9840

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply ID: 9841

- Current leaders receive channelled knowledge
- Founder received channelled knowledge
- Individual members can receive channelled knowledge
- There is a system of formal training to receive channelled knowledge
- There is an informal mentorship system to receive channelled knowledge
- Members learn channelling techniques through self-study

Notes: The leaders in the New Covenant Church rely on Jesus Christ as their source of authority. The essence of the movements discipleship efforts is train members to rely on Jesus Christ as their model.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is 'scientific consensus' valued as a source of knowledge?

ID: 9842

— Yes

Notes: The movement believe in the working together of faith and science. This is evidence in their reliance on drugs and other medical supplies during their community outreaches.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement take positions on empirical sciences such as biology, geology, and astronomy?

ID: 9843

— No

Notes: Generally the religious movement embrace biology, geology, and astronomy to a great extent, as far as it did not contradict their religious believes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this religious movement have a position on evolutionary theory?

ID:

9845

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply

ID: 9846

— Gap creationism (i.e., supernatural creation of life, with potential gaps in the Genesis timeline allowing for Earth's scientifically established age)

Notes: The movement often try to explain the scientific approach to creation from the light of the Biblical creation narrative.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have beliefs that would generally be considered conspiracy thinking?

ID: 9847

Conspiracy thinking refers to explanations for events which propose the existence of a conspiracy, containing knowledge contrary to current consensus.

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement? ID: 9848
"Some truths are objective rather than relative."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: Truth such as immortality of the soul, salvation in Christ alone and eternal reward are unchanging in the belief system of the group and they are not treated as relative.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about the texts of the religious movement that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9849

— Specify: The group believes the Bible teachings on human salvation is for all humans irrespective of age, race and culture.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Media and Public Relations

Does the religious movement use print media? ID: 9850

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9851

— Books

— Fliers/pamphlets

— Journals

— Magazines

— Newsletters

Notes: The New Covenant Church do not underestimate the importance of the print media and carrying out their programmes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of print media? ID: 9852

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9853

- Prayer request systems
- Proselytising/Recruitment
- Reputation management/Public relations
- Scripture
- Selfless service
- Selling goods or services
- Sharing lifestyle advice
- Sharing health advice and wellness products
- Sharing testimonials
- Witnessing

Notes: There are millions of copies of printed materials from the movement in circulation since inception of the group. These materials include tracts, books by the founder and other leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this religious movement use websites or blogs? ID: 9854

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ List the top three most important religious movement-run websites/blogs: ID: 9855

- Source 1: <https://newcovenantchurchnigeria.org/> (Official hub for Nigeria, including headquarters info).
- Source 2: <https://www.nccworld.org/> (Global/Alternative information site).
- Source 3: <https://www.new-covenant-church.com/> (Features online services and resources).

–Other:: <https://www.facebook.com/nccnigeriahq/>.

Notes: These websites are put into active use by the group for effective communication with people globally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this religious movement use traditional broadcast media like telephone, radio or television? ID: 9856

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9857

- Advertising on audio media
- Advertising on video media
- Audio recordings (e.g., record, cassette tape, DVD nonbroadcast recordings)
- Radio appearances (on other people's channels)
- Telephone calls (organised by the religious movement)
- Text messages (sent to telephone numbers and not through social media apps)
- Television appearances (on other people's channels)
- Video recordings (e.g., VHS, DVD)

Notes: The field could not verify if the group run their own Radio channels or Television Channels.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of traditional media? ID: 9858

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9859

- Prayer request systems

- Proselytising/Recruitment
- Reputation management/Public relations
- Scripture
- Selfless service
- Selling goods or services
- Sharing lifestyle advice
- Sharing health advice and wellness products
- Sharing testimonials
- Witnessing

Notes: They group actively engage the use of traditional media to reach more people and achieve their set goals of proselytizing and numerical growth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement use social media ?

ID:

Social media includes applications and platforms such as Discord, Facebook, Instagram, Kakaotalk, LINE, Telegram, Tiktok/Douyin, Wechat, Whatsapp, YouTube, X/Twitter, among others.

9860

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ List the main social media platforms this religious movement uses and estimate the size of their following on each (top three):

ID:

9861

- Source 1:: Facebook - New Covenant Church has an active facebook page that communicates announcements, sermons and articles. at least 4600 followers is attributed a one of their facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/nccnigeriahq/>
- Source 2:: Twitter - updates sharing and engagement with followers is actively done on the groups twitter page. A twitter page belonging to one of the over 500 branches of the church has at least 147 followers. <https://x.com/nccifecity>.
- Source 3:: YouTube - Live broadcasts and sermon archives are on the Church YouTube. The movement you tube in Nigeria has over 1700 subscribers: <https://www.youtube.com/c/NewCovenantChurchNigeria>.

Notes: The New Covenant Church has very active presence on several social media platforms at different levels of their organisation structure.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of social media? ID: 9862

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9863

- Prayer request systems
- Proselytising/Recruitment
- Reputation management/Public relations
- Scripture
- Selfless service
- Selling goods or services
- Sharing lifestyle advice
- Sharing health advice and wellness products
- Sharing testimonials
- Witnessing

Notes: The movement ensures that their use of the social media platforms is tailored towards achieving their set objectives/goals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members often subscribe to movement-specific spiritual content or membership sites on social media? ID: 9864

– Yes

Notes: Some of the group members do subscribe to these sites. It however appears that quite a number of members are yet to subscribe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement use other digital media? ID: 9865

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Select all that apply:

ID: 9866

- Paid advertising
- Smartphone apps requiring membership
- Blogs
- Free advertising
- Gamified apps or interactive spiritual tools
- Online games used to contact other players
- Influencer partnerships
- Livestreaming events
- Mass emailing newsletters or listservs
- Podcasts
- Virtual reality, augmented reality or immersive experiences
- Websites
- YouTube

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria is open to the use of any communication channel that will enable her achieve the goal of reaching many more people with their message and to achieve their set objectives.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of other digital media?

ID:
9867

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Select all that apply:

ID: 9868

- Prayer request systems
- Proselytising/Recruitment

- Reputation management/Public relations
- Scripture
- Selfless service
- Selling goods or services
- Sharing lifestyle advice
- Sharing health advice and wellness products
- Sharing testimonials
- Witnessing

Notes: The goal of reaching more people with the gospel of Jesus Christ and discipleship motivates the movement to maximize available means of communication.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this religious movement use other methods to share its teachings?

ID: 9869

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Select all that apply:

ID: 9870

- Architectural Symbolism
- Botanical arrangements
- Computer code or algorithms
- Crystal formations
- Dance choreography
- Dramatic performance
- Drawing, painting or 2D artwork
- Musical compositions
- Photographic revelations
- Symbolic diagrams

Notes: The field could not vary if all the options above are applicable.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement use sponsorship of externally held events (e.g., of spiritual events, cultural festivals or sports teams)? ID: 9871

— Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria does sponsor externally held events. The movement do organise in Ibadan a 3-day annual National Youth Convention event with praise, preaching, sports competition and lots of fun time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this religious movement have strategies for interacting with outside media outlets? ID: 9872

— Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria engages in one-on-one witnessing, street evangelism, open air crusade and so on to reach more people with their message.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this religious movement have strategies for interacting with academia? ID: 9873

— Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria have campus fellowships in close to 100 Nigerian tertiary institutions. They also speak on education policy and issue communiques that promote academic progress.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement directly fund scientific research that validates their beliefs or practices? ID: 9874

— Yes

Notes: The group fund and supports research in the areas of education, food and medicine as tools to reach more people and expand the Kingdom of Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement directly support the academic advancement of members? ID: 9875

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply:

ID:
9876

- Full scholarships
- Partial scholarships
- Establishing educational institutions
- Supporting academic papers by members
- Hosting academic conferences
- Inviting academic speakers
- Hosting intellectual forums
- Publishing in-house academic journals
- Scholarly-based recruitment

Notes: The academic contribution of New Covenant Church is very pronounced in the field of theology. To their credit is New Covenant Commentary Series (a 10-volume series commentary on the New Testament and Journal of New Covenant Theology. In addition to the aforementioned are books and dissertations by authors such as Tom Wells, Fred Zaspel and Jeremy Benbrooks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about media use and public relations that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9877

– Specify: There is nothing important about media use and public relations that has not been mentioned.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Organisational Structure

Leadership

Does the religious movement have a current leader or leaders?

ID:
9880

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Specify the name(s), date(s) of birth, country or countries of origin and primary language(s) of the leader or leaders ID: 9881

– Name(s): Rev Dr Paul Jinadu

– Date(s) of birth: 1942

– Country or countries of origin: Nigeria

– Primary language(s) of the leader or leaders: Yoruba Language

Notes: Rev Dr Paul Jinadu has lived in the United Kingdom for many years.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What is the biological sex of the current leader or leaders? ID: 9882

– Male

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the relationship status of the current leader or leaders known? ID: 9883

– Yes

Notes: Paul Jinadu married Kate, who he met in Bible College in 1966.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9884

– Monogamously Married

Notes: Paul Jinadu is married to Mrs Kate Jinadu for over 60 years.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do the current leaders have children? ID: 9885

– Yes

Notes: Paul and Kate Jinadu has two sons, Philip and Simon.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are the leader's children considered spiritually exceptional? ID: 9886

– Yes

Notes: The Sons of Paul Jinadu, Philip and Simon are both ordained ministers of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do we know how the leadership is appointed? ID: 9887

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply ID: 9888

– Appointment by internal group

– Elder nomination

Notes: The leaders on a general note determines who becomes a leader.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the leadership advised by others? ID: 9889

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How are leaders advised by others? ID: 9890

– Advisory council selected by leaders

– Spiritual guidance or dream visions

Notes: There are elders within the structure of the group that gives appropriate advice when needed and the group also relies on the Holy Spirit for guidance

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is leadership formally under a collective body (e.g., a council of elders, governing committee, or similar group)? ID: 9891

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What is the name of the collective body that governs at the highest level of the organisation? ID: 9892

– Specify: The name of the body that governs at highest level of the organisation is called Council of Conference Pastors.

Notes: They govern at the national level.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How is this leadership group appointed? ID: 9893

– Council appointment

– Democratic election

Notes: The New Covenant Church allows members to elect their National leaders, however the council eventually determine who emerges as the election result is only a guide.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ To what extent does the religious movement agree with the following statement: "Members or disciples are expected to accept the religious leader's pronouncements on all matters without question or dissent."? ID: 9897

– -2 Moderately opposed

Notes: The structure of the organisation allows members to participate in decision making process at different levels.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How many levels exist in the religious leadership hierarchy? ID: 9894

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

Notes: There four basic levels of leadership hierarchy which includes: The General Overseer, The

National Overseer, The Conference Pastor and the Local Church Pastor.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How do people become leaders or reach senior positions in the organisation? ID: 9895

– Appointment by current leader

– Elections by entire adult membership

Notes: People reach senior positions of leadership both by elections and by the discretion of a current leader(s).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What qualities or abilities does the religious movement value in current leadership? ID: 9898

– Educational qualifications

– Knowledge of tradition

– Knowledge of broader society

– Spirit communication

Notes: Leaders are expected to have good training in Christian Theology and must be people filled with and led by the Spirit of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are organisational leadership roles formally appointed on a geographical or regional basis? ID: 9899

– Yes

Notes: Leaders are appointed to oversee specific region or geographic location.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Membership

Estimated number of members of the religious movement within designated geographical region: ID: 9900

If the estimated number of members is based on external counting (e.g, census report or scholarly assessment), clearly state the source and provide a reference. If the estimate is based on internal reporting by the religious movement, clearly state the source and provide a reference.

– Specify: The church has reported over 50,000 members in Nigeria.

Notes: The Ibadan branch is the largest branch, with a congregation of over 3,000 members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

When the religious movement reports internal demographic data, is it consistent with independent external assessments? ID: 9901

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

When does full membership begin? ID: 9902

– Confirmation or profession of faith

Notes: Membership of the church is open to all born again Christians with the evidence of the new life in Jesus Christ being practically demonstrated.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is the religious movement linked to a specific country or ethnic group? ID: 9903

– No

Notes: Although the group began in Nigeria and was started by a Yoruba man, it however wears a universal look.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members often live communally? ID:

– No

9908

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria does not practice communal living that requires members to sell their houses and live in a common estate. The group like most Nigerian churches emphasises "community" as mutual support, welfare and fellowship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

What is the typical residential environment for members of this religious movement? ID: 9911

– Mixed

Notes: Members are found among all class of people in the society.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

How would you best describe the stability of the religious movement membership? ID: 9912

– Expected to be lifelong, but members can leave

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is membership exclusive, meaning members cannot have other religious affiliations? ID:

– Yes

9913

Notes: Members are expected to be of the Christian religion only and not to have any other religious affiliation outside Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a probationary period before someone becomes a full member? ID: 9914

– No

Notes: Confession of faith in Jesus Christ is the most important factor for membership.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is it possible for members to attend services and events organised by other religious movements? ID: 9915

– No

Notes: Members are not encourage to attend events organized by any other religious movement that is not Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement allow non-members to attend services, take courses, or access teachings? ID: 9916

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Select all that apply:

ID: 9917

- Invited guest
- Lapsed or former member
- Member of the public
- Potential member
- Non-members actively welcome
- Researchers or journalists

Notes: The group is open to all class of people who have good intentions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members permitted to critically examine or challenge the religious movement's literature and directives? ID: 9918

– Yes

Notes: To a moderate extent members can critically examine the religious movement's literature and directives.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

What is the religious movement's approach to members engaging with literature from other religious movements? ID: 9919

– Permitted for education only

Notes: Members may engage with literature from other religious movements if it is not contrary their organizational believes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement set behavioural expectations for its members? ID: 9920

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9921

- Child rearing commitments
- Commitments regarding interactions with other religions
- Dating and marriage commitments
- Dress codes commitments
- Financial commitments
- Time commitments

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there consequences for members who violate behavioural expectations?

ID:
9922

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9923

- Informal disapproval (e.g., shaming, internalized guilt, expressions of disappointment)
- Restricted participation
- Loss of privileges or rewards
- Threats of punishment in the afterlife

Notes: Members are encourage not to violate the moral codes of the organisation most importantly because of divine disapproval and eternal punishment in the afterlife. They may be disciplined by the group to achieve repentance so that the person can be saved from eternal punishment in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement maintain a tiered or differentiated membership structure?

ID: 9924

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement identify key figures other than its leaders or founders who have been important to the self-understanding of members? ID: 9928

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about membership that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9929

– Specify: There is nothing important about membership that has been said.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Minors

Are there minors in the religious movement? ID: 9930

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there children who were born into the religious movement? ID: 9931

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How many generations of children are part of the religious movement? ID: 9932

– Three or more

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do children born into the movement receive full membership status or complete initiation from birth? ID: 9933

– No

Notes: Children born into the movement receive full membership status when they are old enough to decide to be full members by confession of faith in Jesus Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are minors born within the religious movement considered spiritually exceptional? ID: 9934

– No

Notes: There is no exceptional religious status assigned to children born within the New Covenant Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Within the religious movement, are minors thought to have a special role in this lifetime? ID: 9935

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Within the religious movement, are minors thought to have a special role in the afterlife? ID: 9936

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ At what age do minors typically become full members? ID: 9937

– Enter age:: 18

Notes: Although children are part of the covenant community, full, independent membership in New Covenant Church Nigeria is usually confirmed upon personal confession of faith and maturity, often in their late teens

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement provide guidance to its members about raising minors? ID: 9938

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement provide guidelines for educating minors? ID: 9939

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What kinds of education are encouraged for minors? ID: 9940

- Curriculum centred on sacred texts or doctrines
- Curriculum with daily meditation, prayer or rituals
- Education as preparation for movement membership or leadership
- Strong emphasis on the use of technology or the Internet
- Taught by qualified teachers
- University level or higher education

Notes: wholesome education (both religious and secular) is generally encourage for members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are parents encouraged to withdraw their children from 'mainstream' education? ID: 9941

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are minors permitted to have friends outside of the religious movement? ID: 9943

– Encouraged

Notes: Minors are not discouraged from friendship with their peer outside the religious circle.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Who is responsible for disciplining and punishing minors? ID: 9944

- Any adult
- Appointed child-rearing mentors or guardians
- Leaders
- Religious or spiritual figures

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there spiritual or theological reasons given for disciplining or punishing minors? ID: 9945

- Yes

Notes: When minors become disobedient or exhibit deviant behaviour they are reprimanded by their parents at home and by other authority figures within the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What kinds of disciplining and punishing are commonly used on minors? ID: 9946

- Corporal punishment by parents
- Corporal punishment by other adults

Notes: Approach to punishment within the group is relative, it is dependent on the milieu of individuals and families.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there child-focused events like summer camps or youth groups? ID: 9947

- Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church is very committed to children and youth oriented programmes such as summer camps and other youth focused programme.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is having children considered desirable for members or affiliates of the religious movement? ID: 9948

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the movement explicitly pro-natalist, encouraging childbearing to raise its birthrate? ID: 9949

– Yes

Notes: The group expect members to get married and raise children. it will be an aberration for group members to decide not to raise children.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about minors that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9950

– Specify: Nothing important about minors that has not been said.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Growth Strategies

Does the religious movement accept new members or converts? ID: 9951

– Yes

Notes: The movement expects each member to duplicate himself/herself by bringing in a new convert.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are some members of the religious movement expected to engage in proselytising or missionary work? ID: 9952

– Yes

Notes: Group members are encouraged to engage in proselyting. They are deliberately equipped and empowered to win souls and bring them to maturity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement set targets for the number of new members that need to be recruited? ID: 9953

– Yes

Notes: They set the goal of getting at least 1 percent of community members into their church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement reward or recognise members who are most successful in recruiting new members? ID: 9954

– Yes

Notes: Members who are most successful in recruiting new members and disciple them often become cell leaders and eventually pastors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members receive either direct or indirect financial incentives for recruitment? ID: 9955

– No

Notes: There is no practice of financial incentives for recruiting new members. No plaques or cash for member who brought the highest new members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there face-to-face recruitment strategies? ID: 9956

- Campus-based recruitment
- Charity or service events as outreach
- Cultural or musical events
- Missionary trips
- Personal witnessing
- Presence in public spaces, such as malls, markets, transportation hubs or festivals
- Public rallies, such as tent revivals or festivals
- Recruitment through free meals or other forms of hospitality
- Recruitment through youth programming
- Street preaching
- Systematic door-to-door canvassing

– Word of mouth

– Other: The use of social media.

Notes: All available avenues are often utilized to increase membership.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there traditional media recruitment strategies? ID: 9957

– Magazines

– Newspapers

– Print newsletters

– Radio programming

– Television programming

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there Internet-based recruitment strategies? ID: 9958

– Online one-to-one advice, divination or coaching services

– Online groups (e.g., Discord, Telegram or WhatsApp)

– Social media influencer accounts

– Websites

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement target particular groups of people when seeking new members? ID: 9960

– No

Notes: All groups of people are targeted when seeking new members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do new members describe having conversion experiences? ID: 9962

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria expects and teaches new members to give a

description of having a "born again" experience. That is a genuine change of life by the work of the Spirit of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are conversion experiences shared with others in the religious movement? ID: 9963

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are conversion experiences shared with potential new members? ID: 9964

– Yes

Notes: Members freely share their conversion experiences with potential members in New Covenant Church as their discipleship model.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are conversion experiences characterised by: ID: 9965

– Dramatic personal transformations (e.g., restored health or new physical powers)

– Receiving a boon (e.g., wealth, property, possessions or a job promotion)

– Spiritual experiences

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members or leaders use personal testimonies to recruit new members? ID: 9966

– Yes

Notes: Members or leaders do use personal testimonies to recruit new members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How are testimonials used within the religious movement? ID: 9967

– Framed as evidence of supernatural intervention

- Published in books, pamphlets or the Internet
- Shared on social media
- Used as teaching materials for outreach training

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Has the religious movement been accused of using deceptive or manipulative methods in recruitment? ID: 9968

– No

Notes: There is evidence of any accusation that the group uses deception or manipulative methods to recruit members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about growth strategies that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9973

– Specify: There is nothing important about growth strategies that has not been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Movement boundaries

To what extent would this religious movement agree with the following statements: "Movement outsiders cannot be trusted." ID: 9974

– -3 strongly opposed

Notes: The New Covenant Church would not agree with the statement because they actively engage outsiders, they do not isolate themselves.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would this religious movement agree with the following statements: "Movement outsiders are not fully human." ID: 9975

– -3 strongly opposed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage members to view the movement as their family? ID: 9976

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the movement use kinship terms to refer to one another? ID: 9977

– Yes

Notes: The movement normally use terms like, "Brother in Christ", "Sister in Christ", "Father in the Lord" and "Mother in the Lord".

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have negative views toward out-groups? ID: 9978

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement endorse violence towards any out-groups? ID: 9981

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement engage in practices aimed at defending its members or the collective group? ID: 9982

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement employ any specific techniques for self-defence? ID: 9983

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members engage in regular training in self-defence?

ID:
9985

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are members trained in the use of weapons?

ID:
9987

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement use spiritually symbolic weapons?

ID: 9994

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select the type of symbolic weapons used

ID:
9995

– Sword of the Spirit

– The Armor of God (Ephesians 6:10-18)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are individuals encouraged to establish personal defences related to cybersecurity and identity protection?

ID: 9996

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about movement boundaries that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly.

ID:
9997

– Specify: Nothing important that has not been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Leaving or Disaffiliating

Are there formal procedures for leaving the religious movement?

ID: 9998

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Select all that apply:

ID: 9999

- Formal documentation
- Required meeting with leadership
- Written resignation

Notes: The formal procedure mostly apply to those who are saddled with leadership responsibilities. Those who are just members do exit without making it formal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is it possible to be expelled from the religious movement?

ID: 10000

– Yes

Notes: Gross violation of group beliefs and norms consistently without a show of remorse can lead to being expelled from the religious movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are former members treated differently depending on the circumstances of their departure (e.g., lapse, renunciation, or expulsion)?

ID:
10001

– Yes

Notes: Members whose exit happened with the approval and consent of the leadership are treated with more honour and respect.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Primary sources produced by former members:

ID: 10013

Sensitive documents might be held by Inform and accessible upon reasonable request

- Source 1:: Some members leave because Immoral practices of certain leaders.
- Source 2:: Some leave because of geographical relocation to places far away from church branch.
- Source 3:: Dissastifaction with the leadership and administrative structure of the movement.

Notes: Ohah, Nkechi G. & Robinson S. Agbo, " Church Proliferation and Immorality in Nigeria: Interrogating the Paradox", HTS Theological Studies (online version). https://www.scielo.org.za/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0259-94222021000100024. Atoi, Ewere Nelson, "Leadership, Corruption and Poverty in the Nigeria's Neo-Pentecostal Churches." September 2019, 18(1&2):1-17. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349476768_LEADERSHIP_CORRUPTION_AND_POVERTY_IN_NIGERIA%27S_PENTECOSTAL_CHURCHES. Jinadu, Paul, "The Blue Book: Principles & Practice 4th Edition", <https://newcovenantchurchnigeria.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/THE-BLUE-BOOK-4TH-EDITION-JANUARY-2018.pdf>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are former members able to join events or activities as non-members?

ID: 10002

– Yes

Notes: Former members are free to register and attend conferences and other programmes organised periodically.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are former members permitted to maintain social contact with friends and family who remain in the religious movement?

ID: 10003

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are former members regarded as being outside the movement's sphere of spiritual protection?

ID: 10004

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are former members considered evil or dangerous?

ID:
10005

– No

Notes: Former members who leave in the right way are not perceived as evil or dangerous.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do former members report encountering significant barriers when attempting to leave the religious movement? ID: 10006

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about leaving or disaffiliating that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10014

– Specify: The most notable things about leaving the organisation has been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about the organisational structure that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9878

– Specify: There is nothing important about the organisational structure that has not been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Describe or upload relevant documents pertaining to organisational structure: ID: 9879

– Specify: Key Componentsnce leadership. Conference Centre Concept: A matured, self-governing, and self-financing branch capable of pioneering other churches.

Notes: Key Components of the Organizational Structure: Head of the Church: Jesus Christ. General Overseer (G.O.): The overall administrative head, currently working with Associate and Deputy General Overseers. National Council: Comprises the National Overseer, Conference Pastors, and national officers, responsible for administrative oversight. Conference Pastors: Oversee satellite branches, reporting to the National Overseer. Local Branch Pastor/Church: Composed of elders, deacons, and pastors, managing local operations while being accountable to the National/Conference leadership. Conference Centre Concept: A matured, self-governing, and self-financing branch capable of pioneering other churches.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Beliefs and Worldview

General Worldview

Is orthodoxy emphasised?

ID: 10016

— Yes

Notes: They emphasise biblical orthodoxy as foundational. The orthodox emphasis include, that Jesus is Lord, Bible is truth and Salvation is by grace.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement believe in a fundamental unifying principle underlying all spirituality (“concordances”)?

ID:
10017

— Yes

Notes: They belief in the existence of God which is a believe that unify all religions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement teach that all religions are expressions of one underlying truth?

ID: 10018

— No

Notes: The movement express love to everyone irrespective of faith but they do not believe all religions are expressions of one underlying truth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement teach that all mystical experiences point to the same ultimate reality?

ID: 10019

— No

Notes: They do not believe that all mystical experiences point to the same ultimate reality, rather, they believe there is only one true Ultimate Reality: God the Father, Son, Holy Spirit.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement teach that their knowledge represents an “inner teaching” of all religions?

ID: 10020

– No

Notes: They believe the revealed truth been proclaim by them is not in any other religion.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "The universe is a good place."

ID: 10021

– +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: New Covenant Church would agree that God made the universe a good place at creation but the fallen world has made the world not safe/neutral.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "The universe is structured to function effectively and in accordance with its inherent order."

ID: 10022

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They teach that the universe is orderly and governed by divine principles and purpose.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "The universe is seen as existing for an ultimate or greater purpose."

ID: 10023

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The New Covenant Church believes strongly that the universe exists for God's ultimate purpose: to reveal His glory, redeem people through Christ and establish His Kingdom on earth as it is in heaven.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "The universe is regarded as a genuine and objective reality, not as an illusion."

ID: 10024

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The movement treats the world as objective reality. They believe the physical is real and the spiritual is real as well though often unseen.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10025
"The universe is seen as operating on principles that are orderly, consistent and coherent."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe the universe runs on ordered principles set by God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10026
"It is believed that genuine randomness and unpredictability exist within the universe."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: They believe in unpredictability from man's side but order from God's side.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10027
"The world is seen as beautiful."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10028
"The world is seen as interesting and exciting."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The group believes the world is interesting and exciting because God is moving in it. The excitement therefore must be focused on God's kingdom interests, not just adrenaline.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10029
"The world is understood as hierarchical, with elements ranked according to their relative importance."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: They believe that God designed the universe with order and ranks: God first, then man to rule creation, then spiritual authority in church, then priorities in life. They believe rank is about function and responsibility, not about who God loves more.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10030
"The world is regarded as a realm in which nearly everything holds significance."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: New Covenant Church teaches that nearly everything holds significance because God gives it significance not because it is significant in itself.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

How would the religious movement be characterised according to Roy Wallis' 1984 ID:10031
typology of new religious movements?

World-rejecting movements view the wider society as corrupt, impure, or spiritually misguided and seek to withdraw or reject mainstream values. World-Affirming Movements embrace the world and aim to help people flourish within it, often through self-development, personal empowerment or spiritual enhancement. World-Accommodating Movements neither reject nor affirm the world, but instead seek spiritual renewal within existing traditions. They often aim to deepen faith or enhance spirituality without challenging broader social norms.

— World-accommodating

Notes: They believe the world was created good by God but has been corrupted, members are encouraged to live in the world without allowing the corruption to affect them. They therefore live in the corrupt world with the values of their own faith and not the prevailing values of their world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do the religious movement's teachings present the world in dualistic terms, such as ID:10032
good versus evil or spiritual versus material?

— Yes

Notes: They teach "functional dualism" not "philosophical dualism". Their dualistic worldview present categories, it is not a view that hates the physical. There are two kingdoms: God's kingdom versus Devil's kingdom. There are two dimensions: spiritual and physical.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there clear distinctions between good and evil? ID: 10033

– Yes

Notes: They believe the Bible and the Holy Spirit draws a clear distinction between good and evil. Good is seen as obedience to God's word and evil is rebellion against God's Word.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there supernatural beings that are believed to embody or represent this dualism? ID: 10034

– Yes

Notes: They believe in forces of good from God on one side and forces of evil from Satan on the other side. God plus his angels are Kingdom of light and Satan plus demons are Kingdom of darkness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement teach a division between flesh and spirit? ID: 10035

– Yes

Notes: They teach that the flesh is separate from the spirit, that the flesh is mortal and the spirit is immortal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is dualism viewed as complementary energies like yin/yang or Shakti/Shiva? ID: 10036

– No

Notes: There is a clear distinction between the forces of good and the forces of evil. These force are seen as opposing themselves, they are not complementary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this religious movement consider the natural world to be sacred? ID: 10037

– No

Notes: The group perceive the natural world to be created sacred by God but has been polluted by the forces of evil. Non of the elements of the natural world is considered as object of worship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement? ID:10038
"All entities are regarded as possessing consciousness, including animals, plants, rocks, rivers and planets."

— -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The New Covenant Church movement however believe that all entities can become momentary channels through which divinity manifests.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement believe that the universe is imbued with a complex, plural, hierarchical life force ("living nature")? ID:10039

— Yes

Notes: They teach that the world is complex ordered and reflects God's life and wisdom.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members recognise multiple types of life force or energy operating in nature? ID:10040

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is there a concept of different levels or tiers of spiritual beings inhabiting nature? ID:10041

— Yes

Notes: They believe there are forces of good from God and forces of evil from the devil.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is it possible to directly communicate with natural spirits or elementals? ID:10042

— Yes

Notes: They believe that the Spirit of God lives in every member and communicates with

them regularly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members believe that natural disasters reflect the emotional states or disturbances of nature spirits?

ID:
10043

— No

Notes: They believe the causal factors for natural disasters are natural and sometimes are as a result of human activity that violates the law of nature. for example, the depletion of the Ozone layer and increased ultra violet rays of the sun can explain reason for ice melting, ocean surge, increased heat, wild fire and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are animals believed to possess higher spiritual awareness than commonly recognised?

ID:
10044

— No

Notes: Animals are believed to possess a lower spiritual awareness than humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are some places viewed as spiritually stronger or more "alive" than others?

ID:
10046

— No

Notes: Even though there places used for worship, they however believe that God is everywhere and can hear prayers from anywhere.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "Everything is believed to be connected to everything else."

ID:
10048

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The group believe that the world was created by God and is being sustained by Him. They also believe that are things are joined together in Jesus Christ. The believe in biological explanation of Ecological balance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement believe in real and symbolic correspondences between all things in the universe ("correspondences")? ID: 10049

— Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church believe that there is spiritual connection between personal events and spiritual events. it is however not perceive as a one hundred percent direct mirror as is obtainable in astrology.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members believe that events in their personal lives directly mirror cosmic events? ID: 10050

— No

Notes: They believe members life mirrors spiritual realities, not cosmic or astrological realities. They believe planets, constellations, eclipses don't control their destinies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members use divination systems (such as tarot or astrology) based on the belief that microcosm reflects macrocosm? ID: 10051

— No

Notes: The doctrine of the movement oppose members use of divination.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is there a belief that understanding one aspect of nature provides insight into all other aspects? ID: 10052

— Yes

Notes: They believe that revelation and knowledge about God and nature is progressive. They believe the principle in nature can be applied to other aspects of life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members believe that human moral actions have direct consequences in ID: 10053

the natural world?

– Yes

Notes: The believe in the principle of cause and effect.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is there a system of correspondences between different levels of reality (e.g., physical, astral, mental)? ID: 10054

– Yes

Notes: They generally believe that what happens in the spiritual affects the physical and vice versa.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members use sympathetic magic based on the principle "like affects like"? ID: 10055
Sympathetic magic refers to the belief that one can influence a person, object, or event through symbolic actions that imitate or correspond to the desired outcome.

– No

Notes: They don't practice the principle of "like affects like magic". They believe in God who set the principle.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement promote a belief in or aspiration toward returning to a "pure" or original natural state? ID: 10056

– Yes

Notes: The group believe that there will be a new purified world later in the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement express concern for maintaining the health of the environment? ID: 10057

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is stewardship a central concept?

ID: 10058

– Yes

Notes: They believe members should take responsibility of the care of their environment and keep it healthy as part of their stewardship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have a position on climate change?

ID: 10059

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10060

– Accepts climate change and actions undertaken

– Supports climate change mitigation only in line with the goals of the religious movement

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is the religious movement actively involved in environmental activism, such as protests, direct action or land conservation efforts?

ID: 10061

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10062
"People are seen as superior to the natural environment."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe that the human soul unlike other creation is created in God's image and is eternal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10063

"People are seen as part of the natural environment."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe that humans are part of the natural environment because they are part of God's creation, however, they believe that humans are higher in the creation order than all other creation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Humans

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10064
"People are considered inherently good and just."

— -2 Moderately opposed

Notes: They believe that all humans are sinful and have sinful tendencies (have the potential to do evil) and therefore emphasize the need for new life in Jesus Christ as able to restore human ability to be good.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10065
"People are believed to get what they deserve."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: They believe generally that all human actions have consequences. They however believe that sometimes the innocent can suffer the consequences of what they have not done.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10066
"Moral truth is viewed as absolute, not relative."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe the bible based truths for daily living are absolute and not relative.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10067
"People are seen as having more rights than responsibilities."

— -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: They believe that members are beneficiary of God's benevolence and therefore owe Him certain responsibilities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10068
"The universe is believed to need people for something important. "

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe people are God's agents to achieve His purpose in the universe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10069
"Life is seen as offering more pleasure than pain."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: The movement belief only with Christ will life offer more joy and purpose than pleasure. They admit that pain is real and expected.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:
"Gratitude is central to teaching and practice." 10070

N/A for translation

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe being grateful to God is important in all circumstances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:
"Forgiveness is central to teaching and practice." 10071

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They teach that forgiving offenders is important for those who desire God's forgiveness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10072
"Guilt and shame are seen as key elements in living a good life."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: They believe that for sin to be forgiven the sinner must feel guilty, be remorseful and repent from such sinful acts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10073
"It is important to not cause harm to other humans."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They promote peaceful coexistence to a great extent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10074
"It is important to not cause harm to other living beings beyond humans."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: They believe relationship with other living beings should not be cruel. They are allowed to use any living being other than human for food or to meet their daily needs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Supernatural Beings

Do members believe in beings viewed as supernatural?

ID:

— Yes

10075

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are all deities viewed as aspects of one universal divine being ("monism")?

ID:10076

— No

Notes: The believe in one God who is complete in himself - All-sufficient God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there one God or Goddess that is considered a “supreme being”?

ID:

10077

– Yes

Notes: They believe in one Almighty God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10078
"God or the divine is believed to actively intervene in the lives of individuals."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe God is actively involve in the daily lives of humans in providing guidance, protection and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10079
"God or the divine is believed to possess knowledge of how events and the course of evolution will unfold."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe God is responsible for the world and all matter.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10080
"God or the divine is viewed as benevolent, not punitive."

– +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: They actually believe God is both benevolent (to all in offering salvation and other good things) and punitive (when humans disobey his laws).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement believe in multiple kinds of supernatural beings?

ID:10081

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10082

– Angels

– Spirits

– Other:: Demons or evil spirits.

Notes: They do not believe in equating these supernatural beings with God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do God, the divine, or other supernatural beings intentionally interact with the material world? ID: 10083

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do they interact in dreams? ID: 10084

– Yes

Notes: Members believe people experience God in dreams.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do they interact through trance possession? ID: 10085

– Yes

Notes: They believe members can have trance experience in their interaction with God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do they interact in waking, everyday life? ID: 10086

N/A for translation

– Yes

Notes: They believe God can speak to members audibly or through strong inner

impression while awake and in their normal everyday life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do they interact through religious specialists? ID: 10087

– No

Notes: The group believe all members have equal access to interact with God if they maximise the opportunity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do they interact through divination practices? ID: 10088

– No

Notes: The group do warn members against the practice divination.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do they interact through other means? ID: 10089

– Yes

Notes: Simple faith is promoted in the group as a way members can interact with the supernatural.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the movement believe in spiritual warfare or battling evil forces? ID: 10090

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are evil forces or their effects frequently associated with the following factors? ID: 10091

– Antisocial behaviour

– Addiction

– Criminal Behaviour

- Ill health
- Financial misfortune
- Mental illness
- Generalised misfortune
- Poverty

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Can supernatural beings temporarily inhabit or influence a person?

ID: 10092

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Can supernatural possession occur without a person's consent?

ID: 10093

– Yes

Notes: This can happen without a person's full consent especially if the person is not spiritually fortified in Jesus Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Can supernatural possession be seen as beneficial within the movement's teachings?

ID:
10094

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there rituals or methods for inviting a spirit to inhabit a person?

ID: 10095

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does this require training?

ID: 10096

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does this involve an initiation ritual? ID: 10097

— Yes

Notes: Inviting the Spirit of God to inhabit a person simply requires asking in prayer and receiving it by faith.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there specific musical or rhythmic patterns involved? ID: 10098

N/A for translation

— No

Notes: The Spirit comes through just asking in prayer which may or may not involve music.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are specific words, chants or mantras involved? ID: 10099

ritual poll

— No

Notes: It involves just expressing the desire to be filled with the Spirit of God through prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does intentional possession occur in any of the following contexts? ID: 10100

— Invocations

— Prophetic sessions seeking spiritual guidance

— Seasonal festivals or religious celebrations

Notes: Intentional possession is often seen a response to desire and request in prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Can supernatural possession be seen as harmful within the religious movement's teachings? ID: 10101

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ In what contexts do harmful possession appear? ID: 10102

- Bad luck
- Black magic
- Community crises (e.g., times of disease or natural disasters)
- Evil eye
- Ill mental health
- Ill physical health
- Life crises
- Marriage
- Sexual deviancy

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement attempt to remove spirits believed to be possessing humans? ID: 10103

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10104

- Chanting, singing or ritual music
- Ritual ceremony (e.g., exorcism)

Notes: The group believe evil spirits possessing humans can be removed (cast out) through deliverance prayers (that often involve singing, chanting and biblical quotation ritual).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is temporary spirit possession connected to social status within the movement? ID: 10105

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is that social position generally of a higher status? ID: 10106

– Yes

Notes: The group have high regard for members who show manifestation of being filled with the spirit of God but members who are perceived to be filled with evil spirits are viewed from a negative perspective.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is that social position generally of a lower status? ID: 10107

– No

Notes: The social position for members who are perceived to be filled with Spirit of God is often a higher one because such infilling enable members to do the extra-ordinary like heal the sick, cast out demons, see visions and prophesy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are certain types of people more likely to be inhabited by spirits? ID: 10108

– No

Notes: They teach that all members are expected to desire to be filled with the Spirit of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are beliefs in supernatural cohabitation with humans understood to coexist with material explanations, such as mental or physical health conditions? ID: 10110

– Yes

Notes: The group believe the possession of evil spirits can cause some unstable mental or physical health conditions. However, the group is not oppose to complementing spiritual care with medical care to address such conditions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are false or unauthorised spirit-possession claims punished within the religious movement? ID: 10111

– Yes

Notes: The group strongly disapprove and do rebuke members who seek possession or powers from spiritual sources other than the spirit of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the movement believe physical immortality can be achieved? ID: 10112

– No

Notes: They believe whatever is physical is mortal but the spiritual in immortal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement teach belief in life after death? ID: 10114

– Yes

Notes: The group teach life after death as a core doctrine. Death is believed not to be the end but the door way to another life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement believe in reincarnation? ID: 10115

– No

Notes: The movement rejects reincarnation completely. They do not believe anyone will come back after death as goat, bird or new baby. They believe in life after death but do not believe in multiple lives.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the movement believe it is possible to achieve immortality by virtualising the self, such as through digitally uploading the mind? ID: 10119

– No

Notes: The group believe immortality is possible only after death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are ancestors or the deceased considered important in the religious movement? ID: 10120

– No

Notes: Jesus is the only important person to the faith of the movement who they believe is God but lived as man, died, resurrected and lives for ever.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is salvation emphasised in this lifetime? ID: 10126

– Yes

Notes: They believe God through Jesus Christ offers salvation from sin and judgment to all who believe.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there belief in an afterlife? ID: 10127

– Yes

Notes: The belief in an afterlife is core to the New Covenant Church Nigeria. They believe death ends human earthly assignment not existence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What happens to the physical body in an afterlife? ID: 10128

– Transformed into a non-physical essence

Notes: They believe the mortal body will be exchanged for the immortal in the after life

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Calendar and Time

Does the religious movement use the same calendar system as the dominant one in its country? ID: 10129

– Yes

Notes: They use the Gregorian calendar which is the dominant calendar system in Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement use an alternate calendar to the dominant one in its country? ID: 10130

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

How does the religious movement conceptualise time? ID: 10132

– Predominately linear

Notes: Time is perceived as moving forward from past to present to future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement mark significant dates? ID: 10133

– Specify: They take notes of dates of key events in their lives and church.

Notes: They mark key dates like dates of inception, birth dates, death dates and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the movement teach a creation or origin story? ID: 10134

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria teach the creation/origin story from Genesis. They teach that God created man in His own image: defining man's foundation for purpose, marriage, dominion and stewardship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is the origin of the world closely connected to the origin of the religious movement itself?

ID: 10135

– No

Notes: They believe the world was created thousands of years before the religious movement began.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: "Every event throughout eternity is thought to be predetermined." ID: 10137

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe God has a plan for his creation throughout eternity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: "Events are seen as guided by a higher purpose." ID: 10138

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe that God's purpose/divine plan guides events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

World Transformations and Eschatology

Does the religious movement emphasise a coming transformation of the world? ID: 10139

– Yes

Notes: The group believes they have an assignment to transform the world through God's kingdom principles while they expect God to transform it completely when Christ come back.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have transformational events been anticipated in the past? ID: 10140

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church Nigeria has anticipated transformational events in the past

severally. For example, every beginning of the year in their prophetic culture, they give a theme for the year and prophecy of what God is saying for that year. They anticipate that God will interrupt normal life with sudden transformation by providing Job, healing, open doors, national change and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are specific date or dates given for the transformational event? ID: 10141

– No

Notes: They believe Jesus Christ will come back to rule the world and restore order thereby causing total transformation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Will the expected transformative event be sudden? ID: 10153

– Yes

Notes: They believe in suddenness of events such as the rapture of believers in Jesus Church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement claim the transformative event will restore certain people's rights to their land and governance? ID: 10154

– Yes

Notes: The group believe that God's kingdom restoration will result in raising righteous people to take back government, business, land and influence. They also believe there will be restoration of order to which the Jews will be great beneficiaries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Will specific events precede the transformative event? ID: 10155

– Yes

Notes: They believe events such as wars, famines, evangelization, prayer and so on will precede the transformative event.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10156

- Advancement of science and knowledge
- Astrological signs
- Climate change
- Collapse of social institutions
- Disease
- Displacement of the religious population
- Ecological collapse
- Economic collapse
- Establishment of an empire
- Ethnic cleansing of a place
- Mass migration or refugee crises
- Mass spiritual awakening
- Military defeat
- Military success
- Moral decline
- Natural disasters
- Political turmoil
- Religious persecution
- Religious or spiritual revival
- Return of a divine figure
- Scoffing or ridicule
- Technological breakthrough or failure
- War

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the transformative event tied to a specific location?

ID: 10157

– No

Notes: The transformative event will affect all the world, it is not restricted to specific location.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Should the transformative event be accelerated, if possible? ID: 10160

– No

Notes: It is not in the control of humans to accelerate the transformative events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members of the religious movement need to perform specific tasks to bring about the transformative event? ID: 10161

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group are only expected to pray, proselyte and live right in expectation of the transformative events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Must the leader or founder perform certain tasks to initiate the transformative event? ID: 10162

– No

Notes: They believe only God determines when the transformative event will be initiated.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Will non-members bring about the transformative event through their actions? ID: 10163

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is it possible to prevent the transformative event? ID: 10164

– No

Notes: The group believes the transformative event is already divinely determined, it's a matter of when it will happen not a matter of if it will happen.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the transformative event expected to result from divine or spiritual intervention? ID: 10168

– Yes

Notes: They believe all genuine transformation comes from divine or spiritual intervention first. They believe systems are changed by divine efforts but human efforts is required in it management.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is the transformative event understood as divine judgement? ID: 10169

– Yes

Notes: They believe it will be divine judgment (punishment for wicked people and divine reward for the good people).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What shape will the transformative event take? ID: 10170

- An agrarian paradise, or a return to the pre-fall state
- Establishment of a new political system
- Establishment of a new religious system
- Living in harmony with nature
- No language barriers in communication
- Perfect health
- Resurrection of dead
- World peace

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Will anyone survive the transformative event? ID: 10171

– Yes

Notes: Those who walk in obedience to Christ's Kingdom principles will survive the transformative events.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10172

– A subset of the religious movement's members

Notes: They group claim that only those in the religious movement who live in obedience to the principles of the Word of God will survive the transformative event.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Will individuals have to be in a certain location to survive the transformative event? ID: 10173

– No

Notes: They teach that geographical location is not a key determinants of surviving the transformative event but right spiritual standing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Will members take part in violence or warfare as part of the transformative event? ID: 10176

– No

Notes: They believe that taking part in war is not is not part of the divine plan for members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is a prophetic or messianic person expected to initiate the transformative event? ID: 10183

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in Jesus Christ as the singular initiator of the ultimate transformative event.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is this prophetic or messianic person's whereabouts, or time of their coming, known? ID: 10184

– Coming in an unspecified time in near future

Notes: They believe in the coming of Jesus Christ as the messiah at an unknown time in a near future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is there a known purpose for the prophetic or messianic person? ID: 10185

– Will restore religious traditions

Notes: They teach that the ultimate messianic purpose is restoration of human to God. This implies restoration of worship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about beliefs and worldview that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10015

– Specify: The important things have been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Practices

Communal Ritual Practices

Does the religious movement organise group rituals? ID: 10187

– Yes

Notes: New Covenant Church Nigeria organizes group spiritual practices which they refer to as "ordinances, meetings or corporate prayer".

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What kinds of rituals? ID: 10188

– Communion services

– Empowerment

– Faith healing

– Naming rituals

– Pilgrimage

– Prophecy

- Spiritual counselling
- Spiritual healing
- Thanksgiving services
- Worship and devotion

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ During group rituals, do participants likely experience a sense of *communitas* or collective effervescence (i.e., a spontaneous, egalitarian bond that arises among individuals sharing a liminal experience)? ID: 10189

– Yes

Notes: The movement promotes cooperate worship that involves and engages everyone with a shared emotional and spiritual experiences in prayer, singing, Lord's Supper and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How frequently are members expected to attend group rituals? ID: 10190

– Two to three times a week

Notes: Members are expected to attend Sunday services and at least a midweek service. There are periodic events that bring together different classes of people like youths, women and leaders..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are ritual roles assigned by gender? ID: 10191

– No

Notes: Ritual roles within the movement are assigned irrespective of gender. There is no restriction to which gender can lead prayers, singing or teach.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement organise rituals for major life transitions? ID: 10192

– Yes

Notes: The movement marks major life transitions with public group ceremonies which they refer to as "ordinances, dedications, or thanksgiving".

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply:

ID:
10193

- Baptism for adults
- Birth
- Commitment
- Death
- Marriage
- Naming ceremony
- Ordination

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the ritual include a liminal phase, in which participants occupy an intermediate position between two social or spiritual states?

ID:
10194

– Yes

Notes: There are times when members report experiences of being lost in the spirit during worship services.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is pilgrimage encouraged within the religious movement?

ID: 10195

– Yes

Notes: The group encourage members to participate in pilgrimage to land of biblical events in Israel and neighboring countries. They however encourage spiritual pilgrimage more than physical trips to Jerusalem.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage male and/or female circumcision?

ID:
10196

– No

Notes: The group does not emphasis circumcision in their teachings and discourages female circumcision. Male circumcision however is a common practice among Africans till date.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

– No

Notes: The group does not emphasize circumcision in their teachings and discourages female circumcision. Male circumcision however is a common practice among Africans till date.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement practice body modifications?

ID: 10208

– No

Notes: They discourage modifications of the body as they teach that everyone is beautifully created by God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members regularly use crystals, herbs, alchemical products or spiritual tools?

ID: 10213

– No

Notes: Occasionally however, the group do use the olive oil (anointing oil) as symbol of the power of the Holy Spirit (Spirit of God).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members have out-of-body experiences?

ID: 10217

– No

Notes: Out of body experience is not commonly practiced among members of New Covenant Church

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement practice divination or predict the future?

ID: 10219

– No

Notes: They however believe if God wills he can give revelation of the future to members through dreams, trance and visions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement self-describe as practising magic?

ID: 10221

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in any form of magical practice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement practise death rituals?

ID:

10223

– Yes

Notes: The common ritual for the dead is to mourn the dead, conduct wake-keep and burial services and ensure a decent and befitting burial.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are prayers made over the body after death?

ID:

10224

– No

Notes: The group do not believe in prayer for the death but they do conduct services in honour of the departed.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are death rituals performed by ritual experts?

ID: 10225

– No

Notes: The church pastors do conduct services in honour of the deceased, they do not require any specialist to conduct any ritual over the dead body.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are the religious movement's funeral and burial customs similar to those of the wider community?

ID:

10226

– Yes

Notes: The religious funeral and burial customs of this group is larger similar to that of other Christian religious groups in the wider community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about ritual practices that has not been covered above? ID: 10227
If so, please describe it briefly.

– Specify: Nothing important that has not been mentioned

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Individual Ritual Practices

Does the religious movement have ritual practices for individuals (e.g., prayer or meditation)? ID: 10228

– Yes

Notes: They have rituals refer for as personal disciplines for individuals, which includes: daily devotion, personal fasting, personal prayer, giving and so on.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What are the purposes of the individual ritual practices? ID: 10229

- Alleviating anxiety
- Experience love or bliss
- Express gratitude
- Forgiveness
- Guidance
- Influence worldly events (e.g., weather, harvests, elections)
- Life benefits (e.g., health or happiness)
- Managing mental health
- Material benefits (e.g., wealth, property or promotion)
- Offer praise
- Patience
- Protection
- Reaffirm commitment to the religious movement or supernatural power
- Spiritual transformation or growth
- Surrender to a higher power

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement follow a set schedule for individual rituals? ID: 10230

– Whenever individual need

Notes: The set of schedule for individual rituals are not enforced they are flexibly followed by individuals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is prayer emphasised as central to spiritual progress? ID: 10231

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is viewed as central to spiritual progress in New Covenant Church Nigeria. Everything they teach must start and end with prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is meditation emphasised as central to spiritual progress? ID: 10232

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What kinds of meditation are practiced? ID: 10233

– Recitation of text

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is there structured training in meditation? ID: 10234

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is group meditation an important part of the religious movement? ID: 10236

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is meditation thought to improve health or wellbeing in a scientific sense?

ID: 11410

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Devotional Practices

Are there rituals that express devotion to supernatural beings?

ID: 10237

— No

Notes: New Covenant Church does not have rituals that express devotion to supernatural beings except God. Devotion goes to God alone.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are images of the divine permitted?

ID:

— No

10247

Notes: The group discourages any form of image of the divine because such will be termed as idolatrous among group members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is worship integrated into daily activities?

ID: 10251

— Yes

Notes: Members of the group can sing, meditate, pray, read the Bible and so on as they carry out their daily activities. They teach worship as lifestyle. Beyond the services, worship is who members are all through the week.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members feel or show gratitude to supernatural powers after receiving positive outcomes?

ID: 10252

– No

Notes: Members are taught to show gratitude to God only, not to any other supernatural powers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Transmission

Does the religious movement organise spiritual retreats?

ID:

10274

– Yes

Notes: They do organise retreats, conferences and prayer camps.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement manage or own its own premises for spiritual retreats? ID: 10275

– Yes

Notes: The New Covenant Church (NCC) Nigeria campground is located at NCC Camp Ground, opposite Customs Quarters, Ijokodo-Apete Road, Ibadan, Oyo State. It serves as a major center for the church's activities, including regional teen camps, national youth conventions, and other large gatherings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is a teacher-student (i.e., guru-chela) relationship considered essential for spiritual progress?

ID: 10276

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members believe that interrupting the teaching line has spiritual consequences? ID: 10277

– Yes

Notes: Members are expected to take the hearing and teaching of the bible very seriously to avoid the negative consequences of disobeying it.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there a line of succession that confirms who holds spiritual authority? ID: 10278

– No

Notes: There is no family line of succession for appointing authority figures. Leaders are appointed based on approval from top leaders and nomination of the people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are stages of spiritual development acknowledged? ID: 10279

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members move through formal stages or levels? ID: 10280

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does this resemble an educational syllabus? ID: 10281

– Yes

Notes: The level of spiritual and theological training is important as well as the level of spiritual growth, productivity and maturity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is there a pay structure to advance through formal stages or levels? ID: 10282

– No

Notes: Only leaders (Pastors) fully engaged and staff in the employment of the group receive payment. All other members volunteer their services.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members need to be formally initiated to receive advanced instruction? ID: 10285

– No

Notes: The group has no form of initiation other than confession of faith in Jesus Christ and walking in obedience.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members take vows to keep teachings secret?

ID: 10288

– No

Notes: There is no form of secrecy discovered in the teachings or activity of the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members believe that some knowledge can only be transmitted orally?

ID: 10289

– No

Notes: The group members believe important knowledge can be transmitted orally and in written form.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members believe that some knowledge can only be transmitted energetically?

ID: 10290

– No

Notes: The group believe knowledge can be transmitted in different ways.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members believe that some knowledge can only be transmitted telepathically?

ID: 10291

– No

Notes: The group believes all important knowledge can be transmitted through different means.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Food and Drink

Are certain foods forbidden in the religious movement?

ID:

– No

10292

Notes: The religious group do not forbid the eating of any food as no food is thought to affect their spirituality.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members discouraged or prohibited from eating with non-members?

ID: 10296

– No

Notes: There is no restriction that forbids members from eating with non members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are specific preparation methods required for food to be permitted?

ID: 10297

– No

Notes: There is no specific preparation methods required for food to be permitted.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are specific psychoactive substances forbidden (e.g., alcohol, nicotine, caffeine, or narcotics)?

ID:
10299

– Yes

Notes: Generally the group forbids psychoactive substances such as alcohol, nicotine, caffeine or narcotics.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members encouraged to use substances like alcohol, tobacco, or psychedelics during rituals?

ID: 10300

– No

Notes: The use of alcohol among members is highly discouraged and is not allowed during rituals at all.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about food and drink that has not been covered above? ID: 10303

If so, please describe it briefly.

– Specify: All important things about food and drink has been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Health and Healing

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10304
"Illness is a result of a moral failing."

– +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: The group believe that to some extent moral failing can result in illnesses sometimes but not in all situation and not all illness are a result of moral failing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10305
"Illness is a result of karmic actions."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: New Covenant Church rejects the "Karmic" perception of illness. They do not teach Karma at all.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10306
"Illness is a result of divine judgement."

– +1 Mildly endorsed

Notes: The group believes that divine judgment can cause illness in rare cases, it is not general.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10307
"Illness may be caused by supernatural forces."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The group believes forces of evil do afflict people with sicknesses and disease.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10308
"Medicine helps, but only God or the divine truly heals."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: Members are encouraged to take medicine but ultimately to put their faith in God for healing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10309
"Abortion is always immoral."

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: New Covenant Church Nigeria are opposed to abortion. They believe life begins at conception, so abortion is taking human life and it is viewed as immoral.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10310
"Biomedical institutions are often harmful and immoral."

— -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: They do not teach that biomedical institutions are often harmful and immoral, in fact, they actively partner with them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10311
"Biomedical interventions are helpful but incomplete."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: They believe faith and medicine should be combined. This implies biomedical interventions are not sufficient faith in God must be applied.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement offer healing or therapy to members?

ID: 10312

— No

Notes: The group largely relies on orthodox medicine for healing and therapy of members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is vaccination an important issue within the religious movement?

ID: 10325

— No

Notes: There is no problems at all with vaccination. Members are encouraged to partake in government approve vaccination programmes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have special rules or beliefs about blood transfusions? ID: 10326

— No

Notes: Members are allowed to accept blood transfusion and donate blood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement actively discourage or forbid any medicines, treatments or vaccinations?

ID: 10327

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are sick members ever excluded from the religious movement?

ID:

— No

10329

Notes: Except in situations where a member needs to be quarantined will they be separated from the religious movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "Euthanasia (i.e., deliberately killing those near the end of their lives or with terminal illnesses) is always immoral." ID: 10330

— -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The movement believe death should be allowed to come naturally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have any beliefs or practices for people who are dying (e.g., palliative care)? ID: 10331

– Yes

Notes: The group has clear beliefs and practical care for people who are dying. It includes assurance of God's presence, pastoral care and medical support.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Select all that apply:

ID: 10332

- Dying person should not be left alone
- Euthanasia is never permitted
- Group prayer

Notes: To secure eternal security dying members are encouraged to make their way right with God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage the use of alternative or complementary medicine or therapies? ID: 10333

– No

Notes: The group does not have official rule book that encourage or forbid the use of herbs. They encourage trust in God, not in drug or herb.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have teachings or practices about female reproductive health, including menstruation, pregnancy, and childbirth? ID: 10338

– No

Notes: Members are encouraged to follow common medical guide and avoid sexual immorality.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement believe in posthuman or transhuman transformation, whereby individuals can use technology to transcend human capabilities? ID: 10339

— No

Notes: The teach that members do need to become trans-human but Christlike.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage or mandate physical exercise? ID: 10343

— Yes

Notes: They group encourages physical exercise.They do not mandate it as a doctrine.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How frequently are members encouraged or mandated to engage in physical exercise? ID: 10344

— Several times a week

Notes: Members are encouraged to stay fit by doing exercise regularly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement encourage or mandate its members to play specific sports? ID: 10345

— No

Notes: Members are not restricted to specific sports, they can engage in any sport that does not violate their moral code.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement discourage or ban its members from doing specific sports? ID: 10346

— No

Notes: All sports are allowed as far as it doesn't encourage immorality.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage or mandate members to abstain from physical exercise? ID: 10347

– No

Notes: They believe exercise is part of members stewardship responsibility to help keep the body fit for God's glory.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are specific genres of music prohibited or discouraged? ID: 10349

– Yes

Notes: Music that promotes values that are not consistent with that of the group is discouraged.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have specific teachings or practices involving dance? ID: 10350

– No

Notes: All dances are done moderately as individuals are controlled by the Spirit of God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement promote ascetic disciplines, involving the restriction of desires, pleasures, or material attachments as a means of spiritual advancement? ID: 10354

– Yes

Notes: The group teach ascetic discipline without destruction of oneself. For example is fasting without starvation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ What is the purpose of asceticism? ID: 10355

– Establishing discipline, strength, willpower or moral fortitude

– Spiritual development

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

- ↳ What forms do asceticism usually take? ID: 10356
- Extended periods of prayer or meditation
 - Fasting
 - Sensory deprivation

Notes: Celibacy is generally not encouraged but sexual restrictions are encouraged. Sexual intercourse before marriage and sex outside marriage are discouraged.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

- ↳ Are ascetic practices voluntary? ID: 10357
- Yes

Notes: All ascetic practices are voluntary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

- ↳ Is asceticism practiced only during certain times, like Lent or Ramadan? ID: 10358
- No

Notes: It can happen anytime.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

- ↳ Are exemptions from ascetic practices granted to specific groups, such as minors, elderly or sick people? ID: 10359
- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

- ↳ Do members feel pressure or social expectations to practice asceticism? ID: 10360
- Yes

Notes: When asceticism is encouraged corporately members feel pressured to participate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have members or former members reported being harmed by asceticism?

ID:

10361

– Yes

Notes: There few instances of people affected by prolong fasting.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "Suicide is always immoral." ID: 10362

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The group does not encourage or justify suicide, they see it as immoral.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Has anyone ended their life for religious or ideological reasons to advance the goals of the religious movement? ID: 10363

– No

Notes: Such act is not encouraged within the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about health and healing that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10364

– Specify: None.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Gender and Sexuality

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: "There are two distinct genders." ID: 10365

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: They believe in the male and female gender.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10366
"Gender is a social construct."

— -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The group believe that genders are assigned by God at birth base on sex of a person. God created male and female.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:
"Men and women are equal." 10367

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: The group believe God created the man as the head in a marriage situation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10368
"Men are naturally superior to women."

— +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: Superiority in terms of physical and emotional strength is generally accepted within the group but not in terms of intellectual or spiritual capacity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10369
"Women are naturally superior to men."

— -3 Strongly opposed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10370
"Men have a responsibility to care for women and children."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: Men are encourage to take responsibility for their wives and children.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

How many genders are recognised?

ID: 10371

– Two (man and woman)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

How does the religious movement view gender relations?

ID: 10372

– Distinct and opposite social roles for men and women (complementary and equal)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is transcending gender viewed as a spiritual ideal?

ID:

– No

10373

Notes: The idea of transgender is not encouraged within the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the theology allow equal access to leadership for all genders?

ID:

– Yes

10374

Notes: Based on data from the field, the New Covenant Church Nigeria provides significant, active ministry roles for women, including recognizing them as ordained ministers (Reverends) and leaders. However, in terms of the highest level of pastoral authority, their structure appears to be largely complementarian, often featuring husband-and-wife teams where the husband holds the primary leadership position.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the actual distribution of leadership reflect gender equality?

ID: 10375

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is decision-making equally shared among genders?

ID:
10376

— No

Notes: It is open to all and as anyone is free to contribute without respect for any proportion.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do men and women follow different paths to spiritual advancement?

ID: 10377

— No

Notes: The path to spiritual advancement is same for men and women.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there distinct roles for transgender, non-binary, genderfluid, genderqueer, asexual, third gender or androgynous members?

ID:
10378

— No

Notes: Not permitted within the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is religious instruction gender-segregated?

ID:
10379

— No

Notes: Religious instructions are not necessarily gender segregated except in cases that require peculiarity of each gender.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do men and women participate separately in certain rituals?

ID: 10380

— No

Notes: All religious are done together irrespective of gender.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there male-only social spaces?

ID:
10381

– No

Notes: All space are used generally by both gender except rest rooms (toilets/urinary).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there female-only social spaces?

ID: 10382

– No

Notes: All space are used generally by both gender except rest rooms (toilets/urinary).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there specific behavioural roles assigned to each gender (or agender) within the religious movement? ID: 10383

– No

Notes: However, there are few instances where are opposite gender can not be assigned to led a gender specific group. for example, only a woman will be assigned to lead a women's organisation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Can members express gender in flexible or playful ways?

ID: 10390

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is gender-inclusive language used in the religious movement's teachings or practices?

ID:
10391

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have specific teachings about marriage or partnerships?

ID:
10392

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are in-movement partnerships or marriages strongly encouraged? ID: 10393
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10394
– Monogamous marriage between members
– Hierarchical partnerships (e.g., teacher-student)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement urge members to divorce non-believing spouses? ID: 10395
– No

Notes: Divorce is not encouraged on a general note in the religious movement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement encourage members to marry or formally partner each other? ID: 10396
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all attitudes that apply to pre-marital sex. ID: 10397
– Forbidden

Notes: The disapproves of premarital sex.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there explicit rules about who may marry whom?

ID: 10398

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have teachings about sexuality?

ID:

– Yes

10408

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is celibacy required or encouraged for certain members?

ID:

– No

10409

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are sexual conduct standards different for men and women?

ID: 10411

– No

Notes: Sexual morality is equally promoted for both gender.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is homosexual activity explicitly prohibited?

ID: 10414

– Yes

Notes: The movement prohibit all forms of homosexual activity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are sexual practices within the movement linked to specific rituals or ceremonies?

ID: 10415

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there theological reasons for sexual relationships between leaders and members? ID: 10417

– No

Notes: No sexual relationship between leaders and members is allowed outside the context of a monogamous marriage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are sexual thoughts and behaviours addressed through ritual confession or guidance sessions? ID: 10419

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are sexual fantasies considered sinful or shameful? ID: 10420

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is sexual promiscuity considered sinful or shameful? ID: 10421

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are there specific rituals for sexual purification? ID: 10422

– Yes

Notes: The group expects the sexually immoral to acknowledge their immoral acts as sinful before God, confess, ask for forgiveness and refrain from such acts in the future.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are the religious movement's sexual practices kept secret from outsiders? ID: 10423

– Yes

Notes: However, there are not sexual practices allowed in the group outside marriage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are the religious movement's sexual practices at tension with mainstream conventions? ID: 10424

– No

Notes: The religious movement's sexual practices is not at variance with most christian religious group in Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there teachings about LGBTQI+ identity? ID: 10425

– No

Notes: The movement does not promote the values of LGBTQI+identity at all.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about gender and sexuality that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10427

– Specify: None.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Financial Practices

Are you able to provide information about the financial practices of the religious movement? ID: 10428

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are public financial accounts available, such as company or charity records? ID: 10429

– Yes [specify]: Charity records (annual income and expenditure) are available within the organisation.

Notes: The financial records of the group as a charity organisation in the United Kingdom is available in the public domain. For example as at 31/12/24 income is estimated at 323,758 pounds and expenditure at 381,107 pounds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement maintain bank accounts for holding and managing its funds? ID: 10430

– Yes

Notes: The various branches of the movement have their respective bank accounts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement invest its financial resources in the stock market or similar investment platforms? ID: 10431

– Yes

Notes: The group is not restricted from investing some of their income in government approved investment platforms.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement invest its financial resources in real estate? ID: 10432

– Yes

Notes: The group does buy landed properties and build real structures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement invest its financial resources in 'offshore' companies or shell companies? ID: 10433

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement invest in gold reserves? ID: 10434

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement invest in in crypto currency?

ID:

10435

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement make political donations?

ID: 10436

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Can an estimate be made of the movement's total financial size (e.g., assets or annual income)? ID: 10437

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement operate its own economic system as an alternative to the wider economy? ID: 10438

This includes three aspects: 1) Semi-autonomous financial spheres, such as cooperative enterprises, internal currencies, or communal resource-sharing. 2) Ethical or spiritual economies, replacing profit motives with service, reciprocity, or purity principles. And 3) parallel systems, such as member-run businesses, microcredit schemes, or barter networks.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members required to give up personal assets and fully commit to communal finances? ID: 10439

– No

Notes: Members are allowed to be personal about their financial lives and asset management.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent would an average member describe themselves as “just getting by” financially? ID: 10441

— +1 Very well

Notes: Many members are average income earners.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent do members feel unable to afford basic necessities? ID: 10442

Basic necessities include accommodation, food and utilities.

— +1 Very well

Notes: Many members of the group do feel the pressure of basic needs such as rent, food and medical bills but the church has a designed system to reduce it through empowerment and community support.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent do members feel unable to afford the things they want? ID: 10443

Desirable goods may include clothes, leisure items and pleasurable activities.

— +1 Very well

Notes: Members do feel the gap between what they want and what they can afford but the church teaches them to handle that gap wisely by not being anxious.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent are members likely be able to absorb an unexpected financial shock? ID: 10444

An unexpected financial shock often coincides with life events (e.g., divorce, loss of job, illness, bereavement, natural disasters or unexpected car repairs).

— -1 Somewhat

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent are members likely to have money left over at the end of the month? ID:

— -1 Somewhat

10445

Notes: Many members who live below a dollar per day will struggle to have left over by end of the month.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

To what extent are members likely feel their life choices are limited by their financial situation? ID: 10446

— +1 Very well

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is paying for spiritual or religious courses required for advancement? ID: 10447

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is there a belief that more expensive courses, products or retreats are more powerful or authentic? ID: 10448

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are members pressured to attend courses? ID: 10449

— No

Notes: Attending courses is base on personal decision and will.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are paid retreats (e.g., residential courses) required for spiritual advancement? ID: 10450

— Yes

Notes: Retreat are often organised and members are required to register with minimal cost and also secure paid for accommodation in nearby hotels and guest houses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members typically required to purchase books, materials, spiritual items or spiritual teachings sold by the religious movement? ID: 10451

– Yes

Notes: Members are encourage to buy books, messages and other related items produced by the group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members encouraged to sell materials owned or copyrighted by the religious movement? ID: 10452

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement offer certification for spiritual practices it has developed? ID: 10453

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement consider its name and spiritual materials as intellectual property? ID: 10454

Intellectual property covers copyright, trademarks and patents where an individual or organisation seeks to protect its intangible assets and prevent others from using its name, materials or products, for example.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is regular recertification required for membership? ID: 10455

– Yes

Notes: This is most applicable to the group's educational institutions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is paying for continuing courses required for recertification?

ID:

– Yes

10456

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Do members usually pay for spiritual services (e.g., consultations, blessings, healings or spiritual life activations)? ID: 10457

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members charged attendance fees for workshops, worship services, ceremonies, rituals or other spiritual events? ID: 10458

– No

Notes: No payment is required to attend worship services but specialized sessions or seminars may require some registration.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members encouraged to use businesses run by other members or leaders within the religious movement? ID: 10459

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How do members use businesses run by other members or leaders? ID:

ID:

– Businesses owned by members and open to the public (e.g. insurance, grocery stores or restaurants) 10460

– Courses

– Event organising, festivals or performances

– Healing or therapeutic services

– Life coaching

- Merchandising
- Online platforms and apps
- Publishing or media companies

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are luxury items for leaders purchased by the religious movement or donated by members? ID: 10461

– Yes

Notes: Luxury items are sometimes purchase by the religious movement and they could also be donated.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is internal employment or ordination considered more ethical than working outside the religious movement? ID: 10462

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members encouraged to make financially risky choices in pursuit of a more spiritually valued life? ID: 10463

– No

Notes: Members are encourage to give in form of free will donations, tithes and offerings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is earning substantial income viewed as important or spiritually beneficial? ID: 10464

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is entrepreneurship viewed as important? ID: 10465
 Entrepreneurship is the process of starting and running a new business.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are members encouraged to establish spiritually or ethically oriented businesses? ID: 10466

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are spiritually or ethically oriented businesses run by members financially independent from the religious movement (i.e., profits are not shared or paid as fees to the organisation)? ID: 10467

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are members encouraged to develop personal brands that reflect their personality, personal skills or spiritual attainment? ID: 10468

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are members encouraged to become influencers on social media? ID: 10469

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement offer courses on marketing, branding or advertising? ID: 10470

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does income flow upward from income-generating members to higher leadership, similar to a multi-level marketing (MLM) model? ID: 10472

– No

Notes: The flow of income is not like the multi-level marketing model because they are non-profit organisation. The members are expected to give offering, tithes and donation to the church or branches for the work of the movement. The branches in turn gives 15 percent (at most) of their income to support the higher body. They may also give other contribution to meet general needs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage donations? ID: 10473

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ How often are members asked or expected to contribute financially? ID: 10474

– Weekly

Notes: Freewill offerings, tithes and donations are collected at least weekly. But generally members give as they are opportune to give.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Do members believe that generosity or donations result in greater personal prosperity? ID: 10477

– Yes

Notes: They generally teach that giving generously attracts divine blessings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are appeals for donations regularly made in emotionally charged or rousing settings? ID: 10478

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the religious movement track or record individual members' donations or tithes? ID: 10480

– No

Notes: Records of individual members donations or tithes are kept majorly for the purpose of accountability.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Is shame ever used to encourage or increase donations? ID: 10481

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are individuals encouraged to make financial commitments to the religious movement based on aspirations rather than present financial means? ID: 10483

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Are members encouraged to make financial donations for specific project or causes? ID: 10485

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10486

- Educational programs or scholarships
- Emergency funds for natural disasters, ill health or misfortune (for members)
- Emergency funds for natural disasters, ill health or misfortune (for non-members)
- Environmental or conservation projects
- Charitable causes unrelate to the religious movement
- Missionary or outreach activities
- Poverty reduction

– Temple building, building repairs or building of other institutional structures

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members experiencing financial hardship viewed as morally inferior or responsible for their situation (e.g., due to bad karma, weak faith, or insufficient spiritual investment)? ID: 10487

– No

Notes: Members experiencing financial hardship are often given necessary spiritual, moral and financial support that can bring them out of their predicaments.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement encourage members to support other members who are struggling financially? ID: 10488

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual support is also encouraged to deal with forces of evil that may cause financial problems.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10489

- Direct financial support to members by the religious movement
- Direct financial support between members
- Material support (e.g., housing, meals, childcare, or household assistance)
- Social support (e.g., job offers, employment opportunities, or professional networking)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members ever encouraged to make personal donations that could reduce their financial independence or affect their dependents' inheritance? ID: 10490

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are members encouraged to work for the religious movement as unpaid volunteers? ID: 10491
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ On what basis do members participate in unpaid volunteering? ID: 10492

– As part of communal living

– For the direct financial benefit of the religious movement

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Does the time spent on unpaid volunteer work limit members' ability to earn an income outside of the religious movement? ID: 10493

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement offer investment advice, loans, financial schemes, or financial products exclusively for members? ID: 10494

– No

Notes: The movement is not a financial institution but do invite experts periodically to guide members in this regard with good financial literacy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about financial practices that have not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10498

– Specify: None

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about practices that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10186

– Specify: None

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Legal Issues

Legal Status

Is this religious movement involved in legal issues/cases?

ID: 10499

— Yes

Notes: They are being sued and can also sue others who violate their rights.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have there been any legal cases against the religious movement?

ID:

10500

— Yes

Notes: <https://lite.judiciary.gov.ng/case/fo-loy-v-registered-trustees-of-the-new-covenant-church-appeal-2017> judy.legal Login Register KOLAWOLE F.O-LOY ESQ. V. REGISTERED TRUSTEES OF THE NEW COVENANT CHURCH (2017) JELR 38158 (CA) Court of Appeal · CA/1/231/2011 · 10 Mar 2017 · Nigeria Coram MONICA BOLNA'AN DONGBAN-MENSEM JCA MODUPE FASANMI JCA CHINWE EUGENIA IYIZOBA JCA Appearances KOLAWOLE F. O. LOY, ESQ. in person For the Appellant; KUNLE ISHOLA, ESQ. with him, DAMILOTUN OGUNLEKE, ESQ. For the Respondent. Judgement CHINWE EUGENIA IYIZOBA, J.C.A. (Delivering the Leading Judgment): This is an appeal against the Judgment of OluGbemi J. of the High Court of Ogun State Ijebu-Ode in Suit No. HCJ/188/2007 delivered on the 17th day of May, 2011 wherein the learned trial Judge granted most of the reliefs claimed by the Respondent and dismissed the Appellant's counterclaim. The facts leading to the institution of this suit is somewhat complex and need to be carefully set out for better understanding of the issues involved. The Respondent herein claims that sometime in 1999, it bought two plots of land, Plots 1 and 2 Block C Ladejobi Layout, off Ibadan Road, Ijebu-Ode from one Kehinde Ladejobi, one of the children of Chief F.A. Ladejobi the deceased original owner of the entire Layout. The Respondent claimed that the said son Kehinde Ladejobi had represented to its representative, Pastor Olatunde Owolabi that the two plots of land were his own portion of the Estate of their deceased father.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Criminal Cases

Has the state initiated any criminal cases against the religious movement or its members?

ID:

10501

— No

Notes: The religious movement have not been found to be involve in any criminal acts for which they were sued.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Regulatory Cases

Have there been any other court cases against the religious movement for breaking laws or regulations? ID:10521

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Civil Cases Against the Movement

Have there been any civil cases against the religious movement or its members where financial compensation was sought? ID:11412

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply: ID:10510
– Property disputes

Notes: Record of property dispute exists.

↳ Did any of these civil cases have real substance or lead to changes in the practices of the religious movement? ID:11413

– No

Notes: The issues are not serious enough to affect the groups practices or lead to change.

↳ Were fines imposed on the religious movement by the court? ID:10525
– Field Doesn't Know

Movement-Initiated Cases

Have any legal cases been started by the religious movement?

ID: 10526

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have any legal cases been threatened (but not formally initiated) by the religious movement?

ID: 10531

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have there been any civil cases where the religious movement or one of its members filed a lawsuit against someone else?

ID: 10532

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10533

–Other:: The lawsuits filled by the movement as discovered in the field is in respect to landed property.

Notes: Registered Trustees of the New Covenant Church (Nigeria): This entity has been involved in litigation regarding property disputes in Nigeria, including a 2017 appeal concerning land ownership in Ijebu-Ode.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

↳ Were the offenders required to pay fines or damages to the religious movement or its members?

ID:

10534

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Family Law

Have there been any family law cases, such as divorce, child custody, adoption, or spousal support, where the beliefs and practices of the religious movement were an important part of the case? ID: 10513

— No

Notes: The believe and practice of the group about issues of the family in respect to divorce, child custody, adoption and so on to a great extent aligns with that of the state.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have there been any family law cases initiated by a member, such as divorce, child custody, adoption, or spousal support, where the beliefs and practices of the religious movement were an important part of the case? ID: 10535

— Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Rights and Freedoms

Have the religious movement or any of its members started legal cases about freedom of religion or the exercise of religious or human rights? ID: 10542

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Allegations of Harm to Members

Are there claims that the religious movement has interfered with investigations meant to prevent harm? ID: 10546

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there claims that the religious movement has engaged in coercive control of its members? ID: 10547

Coercive control entails an act or a pattern of acts of assault, threats, humiliation and intimidation or other abuse that is used to harm, punish, or frighten a victim. This includes behaviours designed to dominate,

isolate and control another person. It can involve physical, emotional, financial or spiritual elements.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Are there claims that the religious movement has engaged in other potentially criminal offences that have not resulted in court proceedings?

ID:
10548

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Has the religious movement made any reports or statements in response to accusations of wrongdoing?

ID:10551

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Has the religious movement changed any of its practices or teachings because of allegations of harm?

ID:10560

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Does the religious movement have established procedures for safeguarding and protecting whistle-blowers?

ID:10558

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Have whistle-blower reports caused major changes within the religious movement? ID:10559

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Libel and Slander

Has the religious movement sued for libel, defamation or slander?

ID: 10552

– Field Doesn't Know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Is there anything important about legal cases that have not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly.

ID: 10561

– Specify: All the basic information about legal cases have been covered above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria